

Bluesky as a Social Media Data Source for Disaster Management: Investigating Spatio-temporal, Semantic and Emotional Patterns for Floods and Wildfires

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Abstract

Social media has become a key data source for near-real-time disaster monitoring and response, with Twitter playing a central role for over a decade. However, recent [Application Programming Interface \(API\)](#) changes on Twitter (now: X) have restricted academic data access, creating an urgent need to identify viable alternatives. This study investigates the suitability of the decentralised social media platform Bluesky for disaster-related geo-social media analysis, aiming to evaluate whether it can serve as a viable alternative microblogging platform for spatio-temporal disaster monitoring. Using a keyword-based crawling pipeline, we collected 676,337 posts related to two major natural disasters: the September 2024 Central Europe floods and the January 2025 Southern California wildfires. We applied a multilingual analysis pipeline covering semantic, emotional, geospatial, and temporal modalities. It includes disaster-relatedness classification, emotion detection, geoparsing and subsequent spatio-temporal aggregation. Our results show that disaster-related content on Bluesky surged in direct response to the disasters, peaking at up to 80% of daily posts during

the main impact phases. Emotional expressions, particularly fear and anger, rose sharply alongside event progression. Geospatial analysis of the geoparsed data revealed heightened disaster-related posting activity in affected areas, demonstrating the platform’s utility for geographic disaster monitoring. However, large differences between urban and rural regions, as well as between different countries, were identified. Furthermore, we demonstrate current platform limitations such as user penetration, [API](#) constraints and sensitivity to keyword selection.

Keywords: geo-social media, disaster management, spatio-temporal analysis, natural language processing, geoparsing, emotion analysis, semantic analysis

1 Introduction

Social media platforms provide a near-real-time stream of crowd-sourced information across the world. As such, they have become a valuable data source in disaster management, enabling timely access to reports, observations, and public sentiment during crises (e.g. [Lei et al., 2025](#); [Resch, Usländer, & Havas, 2018](#)). Among these platforms, the microblogging service X (formerly Twitter) has historically played a central role ([Beigi, Hu, Maciejewski, & Liu, 2016](#)), largely due to its open academic [Application Programming Interface \(API\)](#) and the availability of geotagged content, which offered high-quality geospatial information ([Steiger, Westerholt, Resch, & Zipf, 2015](#)). However, recent changes in the corporate strategy of X have led to significant restrictions in [API](#) access for researchers ([Murtfeldt, Alterman, Kahveci, & West, 2024](#)), creating an urgent need to identify viable alternatives.

Alternative platforms such as TikTok, Reddit, Instagram, YouTube and Telegram have been explored in disaster contexts (e.g. [Blackwood, Hardy, Dodd, Ooi, & Williams, 2023](#); [Hladík, Herman, Snopková, & Konečný, 2024](#); [Liu, Zhao, Zhan, & Hernandez, 2024](#); [Vračević, Schmidt, Keskin, Kanilmaz, & Resch, 2025](#)), but each presents specific challenges in terms of data accessibility and content quality. For example, TikTok’s Research [API](#) currently only yields video metadata like descriptions. Furthermore, data collection is limited to a 30-day time window, making large-scale and temporally comprehensive analysis difficult ([Corso, Pierri, & De Francisci Morales, 2024](#)). Conversely, discussions on Reddit are typically text-heavy and asynchronous, while Telegram requires predetermined lists of channels to crawl. Platforms by Meta, such as Instagram, offer no official academic [API](#) access, and YouTube is restricted to video metadata. More generally, most studies based on social media platforms beyond Twitter tend to rely on limited samples. Simultaneously, they typically pay little attention to the geospatial dimension (e.g. [Razavi & Rahbari, 2020](#); [Ruan, Kong, McBride, Sethjwala, & Lv, 2022](#)). As a result, the current landscape of disaster-related social media research is fragmented, and there remains a critical gap in identifying and evaluating platforms that support robust, geographically grounded research.

Potentially addressing this gap, Bluesky has emerged as a promising substitute for Twitter in social media research. The decentralised microblogging platform was publicly launched in February 2024 ([Kleppmann et al., 2024](#)) and has since seen rapid user

growth. It provides access to a broad stream of user-generated content via the highly functional search and firehose [APIs](#). These [APIs](#) include metadata like timestamps, language, user identifiers, and attached media at the post level. Previous studies have examined Bluesky’s user growth, structural dynamics, and political discussions ([Balduf et al., 2024](#); [Failla & Rossetti, 2024](#); [Jeong, Jiang, Tan, Bernard, & Liu, 2024](#)). So far, however, no study has systematically assessed its suitability for disaster response or explored the geospatial characteristics of its content.

In this paper, we explore the suitability of Bluesky for geographically grounded social sensing in disaster scenarios through a comparative analysis of two recent high-impact natural disasters: the September 2024 Central Europe floods and the January 2025 Southern California wildfires. Using a custom keyword-based crawling pipeline, we collected 676,337 posts and processed them through a multilingual analysis framework that includes geoparsing, semantic disaster-relatedness classification and emotion detection. Our research thus addresses the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How suitable is the social media platform Bluesky as a data source for geo-social media analysis for disaster management?
- **RQ2:** To what extent can location mentions in Bluesky posts support geospatial analysis of disaster-related content?
- **RQ3:** What semantic, emotional, spatial, and temporal patterns emerge in disaster-related Bluesky posts?

Our key contributions are as follows:

- We present the first comparative analysis of Bluesky content in two major natural disaster scenarios.
- We develop a custom keyword-based data collection pipeline designed to effectively obtain posts through Bluesky’s [API](#).
- We perform large-scale geoparsing to extract and evaluate the geographic distribution of location mentions in disaster-related content.
- We analyse geospatial and temporal posting patterns to identify trends and differences in user activity across the two disaster events.
- We examine the emotional tone and disaster-relatedness of posts over time using multilingual [Natural Language Processing \(NLP\)](#) models.
- We critically assess the potential and limitations of Bluesky for geospatial disaster analysis and propose directions for future research.

2 Related work

Social media data has long been utilised in the context of natural disasters and associated disaster management activities, particularly since the 2010 Haiti earthquake [Beigi et al. \(2016\)](#). So far, the majority of the published studies have been based on Twitter data, which is attributable to the existence of an open [API](#) with access to georeferenced data. Due to this focus on Twitter, methodological developments such as algorithm fine-tuning were also mainly developed for short social media texts. In

May 2023, however, Twitter (now: X) implemented changes to its [API](#) that significantly limited data accessibility for researchers, thereby undermining its traditional status as the primary platform for social media analyses ([Murtfeldt et al., 2024](#)).

While there has been a clear focus on Twitter data, a few studies have explored the application of other social media platforms for disaster-related studies. For instance, [Basch, Yalamanchili, and Fera \(2022\)](#) analysed views and comments for 100 climate change-related TikTok videos. [Liu et al. \(2024\)](#) conducted a narrative analysis of emotional reactions to wildfires in Hawaii based on 526 TikTok videos and 59,950 comments. [Stimpson, Srivastava, Tamirisa, Kaholokula, and Ortega \(2025\)](#) investigated 275 TikTok videos for the same event, finding high engagement rates for posts containing misinformation. [Ben-Enukora et al. \(2025\)](#) studied climate change-related TikTok videos in Nigeria, identifying polarisation tendencies. Using an ethnographic, qualitative approach, [Blackwood et al. \(2023\)](#) found that the visual representation of wildfires in Tasmania on Instagram is primarily aesthetically pleasing, with limited focus on destruction or human suffering. In a study on the 2019 Iranian floods, [Razavi and Rahbari \(2020\)](#) manually assigned topics to 12,000 Telegram posts, focusing on the mentioning of toponyms. [Hladík et al., 2024](#) used YouTube’s Data [API](#) to harvest and investigate video metadata for spatio-temporal patterns in disaster impact and recovery regarding the 2021 tornado in southern Moravia, Czechia. There have also been a few papers comparing data from different social media platforms: [Ruan et al. \(2022\)](#) found differing topics and sentiments between data from Twitter and Reddit regarding the 2019 Ridgecrest earthquake sequence in California. Similar differences were also observed between Twitter and Telegram data ([Razavi & Rahbari, 2020](#)). [Vračević et al. \(2025\)](#) compared data from TikTok, Telegram, Reddit, Mastodon, and Twitter for the 2022 Hurricane Ian. While they found similarities regarding the spatial and temporal distribution of posts, they argued that no platform can fully replace Twitter, primarily because of the low spatial accuracy of geoparsing outputs. In summary, social media research on natural disasters without Twitter data typically relies on limited sample sizes, emphasises qualitative approaches, and often overlooks the spatial aspects of the data.

Given that Bluesky was a fairly new social media platform at the time of this study, there were still relatively few analyses focused on it. [Balduf et al. \(2024\)](#) collected the first large-scale dataset from Bluesky, consisting of 225 million posts from over 5.5 million users. However, they did not conduct a semantic analysis of the post contents, but rather focused on structural elements of the platform. [Failla and Rossetti \(2024\)](#) gathered 235 million posts, showing a considerable increase in posting activity, as well as language clusters for English, Japanese, and German. Based on user profile data, they revealed that 39% of follower/followee relationships are reciprocal. Furthermore, they applied topic modelling and sentiment analysis to an English subset. [Jeong et al. \(2024\)](#) analysed user interactions on Bluesky from a temporal perspective, showing steady growth and the emergence of semantically similar user communities. [Reddy and Ciampaglia \(2025\)](#) found that reliable news are posted on Bluesky, but that they originate mainly from left-leaning authors. [Arroyo-Machado, Robinson-Garcia, and Torres-Salinas \(2024\)](#) demonstrated that the use of Bluesky to promote research

efforts has increased considerably, suggesting a rising importance for academic dissemination. Similarly, Ruiz-Bravo (2025) showed a transition of users from Twitter to Bluesky. Brown, Onik, and Baggili (2024) analysed Bluesky with regard to cybersecurity topics, identifying some security concerns such as plaintext passwords. To our knowledge, no study has yet considered the spatial dimension of Bluesky content.

3 Materials and methods

This study investigates the potential of Bluesky as a source of situational awareness during natural disasters. As illustrated in Fig. 1, our methodology comprises five main steps: (1) data collection through temporal and keyword-based crawling of Bluesky posts, (2) geoparsing of post texts to extract spatial information, (3) classification of disaster-relatedness, (4) multilingual emotion detection, and (5) spatio-temporal aggregation and analysis.

Fig. 1 Methodological workflow of the study.

3.1 Data collection

To evaluate the suitability of Bluesky for disaster response, we considered two recent real-world disaster events: the September 2024 floods in Central Europe and the January 2025 wildfires in Southern California (USA). The two disasters can be detailed as follows:

1. In mid-September 2024, Storm Boris, a cut-off low-pressure system, brought heavy rainfall to Central Europe, resulting in severe flooding across Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Romania and Hungary. In the five days from September 12 to 16, record precipitation ranging from 300 to over 400 mm was observed in some regions. The floods led to at least 27 fatalities and caused widespread infrastructural damage, with estimated economic losses of 4.2 billion euros (Austrian Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism, 2024; Maskell, 2024).
2. Between January 7 and 31, 2025, 14 wildfires occurred in Southern California, affecting the Los Angeles metropolitan area and San Diego County. The

fires occurred under conditions of drought, low humidity, dense vegetation, and extremely dry Santa Ana winds reaching up to 160 km/h. They caused at least 30 fatalities, displaced over 200,000 people, destroyed more than 18,000 structures and burnt over 230 km² of land (California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection, 2025; US EPA, 2025).

Both disaster events were widely discussed on social media (e.g. Erokhin, 2025), but it remains unclear to what extent they generated activity on Bluesky. Given the platform’s rapid growth during the study period, from approximately 10 million users in September 2024 (Bluesky, 2024a), to 15 million in November 2024 (Bluesky, 2024b), and 30 million by January 2025 (Bluesky, 2025), the volume and nature of disaster-related posts varied between the two events.

3.1.1 Crawling

To collect data for the two specified disasters, we used the `app.bsky.feed.searchPosts` API endpoint, which allows for textual queries through character-wise matching and temporal filtering. Unfortunately, the `cursor` query parameter was not functional as of June 2025 (bluesky-social GitHub, 2024). The endpoint was therefore limited to returning a maximum of 100 posts per query. Therefore, we implemented a custom algorithm that iterates over a specified time frame based on a set of keywords. It is described in Algorithm 1 and operates based on a list of keywords Q , and a time interval $[t_{\min}, t_{\max}]$. For each keyword, the algorithm iterates over the time interval in steps of s minutes. In preliminary runs, we found that a value of $s = 30$ minutes consistently returned fewer than 100 posts across the selected keywords and time ranges. This suggests that this interval was sufficiently granular to avoid any data truncation as a result of the API’s per-query result limit. We thus adopted $s = 30$ as the step size in our crawling configuration.

Algorithm 1: Crawling logic used to obtain posts from Bluesky based on temporal and keyword filtering.

Input: keyword list Q , time interval $[t_{\min}, t_{\max}]$, crawling interval s in minutes
Output: A set of Bluesky posts P
 $P = \{\}$;
foreach *keyword* q **in** Q **do**
 for *time* t **from** t_{\min} **to** t_{\max} **in steps of** s **do**
 posts = `app.bsky.feed.searchPosts`($q = q$, since = t , to = $t + s$, limit = 100);
 $P = P \cup$ posts;
 end
end
return P

With this setup, we crawled data for the two events of interest. We stored all available fields, including the post text, language, posting date, user identity strings, links to external websites and embedded images, as well as the number of replies, reposts, and likes.

2024 Central Europe floods.

For the Central Europe floods, we collected Bluesky posts published from September 5 to September 30, 2024, using the keyword-based crawling method described in Algorithm 1. This event presented particular linguistic challenges, as it spanned six countries with various official languages. To account for this, we used a multilingual keyword set, similar to what has proven effective for filtering Twitter data (Hanny, Schmidt, & Resch, 2024). The keyword list included 52 terms related to flooding, environmental conditions, along with impact and response terms in English, German, Czech, Slovak, Polish, Romanian, and Hungarian.

- **Event types (multilingual):** *flood, flut, überschwemmung, hochwasser, povodeň, zaplavení, zaplaveni, powódź, zalenie, inundatie, inundare, árvíz, elöntés*
- **Location terms:** Given the widespread nature of the floods across Central Europe, we refrained from using specific location names to reduce the risk of introducing geographic bias and to ensure broader regional coverage across all affected countries.
- **Environmental conditions (multilingual):** *rain, regen, déšť, dážď, deszcz, ploaie, eső, boris*
- **Impact and response (multilingual):**
 - *evacuation, evakuierung, evakuace, evakuácia, ewakuacja, evacuare, evakuálás*
 - *rescue, rettung, záchrana, ratunek, salvare, mentés*
 - *fatality, todesfall, úmrtí, ofiara śmiertelna, deces, haláleset*
 - *damage, schäden, škody, szkody, daune, kár*
 - *economic losses, verluste, ztráty, straty, pierderi, veszteségek*
- **Hashtags:** At the time of data collection, Bluesky had limited uptake of event-specific hashtags in Central Europe. As such, no consistent or widely used hashtags were identified during preliminary searches, and they were therefore not included in the keyword set.

In total, we were able to collect 105,767 unique posts for the Central Europe floods use case.

2025 Southern California wildfires.

For the Southern California wildfires, we collected Bluesky posts from December 24, 2024 to February 14, 2025, again using Algorithm 1. In contrast to the floods, this event was geographically and linguistically more localised. As a result, we employed a more extensive and diverse keyword list of 25 terms. Keywords were curated based on Hanny et al. (2024) and manual searches of relevant posts during the disaster period.

- **Event types:** *fire, wildfire, firestorm, brush fire, forest fire, blaze, inferno,*
- **Location:** *southern california, los angeles, san diego, soocal,*
- **Environmental conditions:** *santa ana, drought, low humidity, red flag warning,*
- **Impact and response:** *evac, fatality, homes destroyed, smoke plume, air quality*
- **Hashtags:** *#californiawildfires, #cafire, #soocalfires, #sandiegofire, #santaanawinds*

This approach yielded 570,570 unique posts, which is significantly more than for the floods use case. The higher volume reflects both the growing user base on Bluesky in early 2025 and the platform’s demographic concentration in the [United States of America \(USA\)](#). More specifically, in November 2024, 42.27% of all Bluesky visits originated from the [USA](#), followed by Brazil (11.01%), the [United Kingdom \(UK\)](#) (7.51%), Japan (6.18%), and Germany (3.21%) ([Duarte, 2025](#)). By March 2025, the [USA](#) share had grown to 73.99%, further skewing platform activity towards North America ([Semrush, 2025](#)). It also highlights differences in language coverage, which likely contributed to the higher post volume, too.

3.1.2 Ground reference data

To relate the social media activity to the actual natural disaster events, we obtained active wildfire and flood delineations for the two events. For the September 2024 Central Europe floods, we used the Copernicus [Global Flood Monitoring \(GFM\)](#) system to obtain flood delineations between September 5 and September 30, 2024. [GFM](#) provides continuous monitoring of floods at a spatial resolution of 20 m by processing Copernicus Sentinel-1 [Synthetic Aperture Radar \(SAR\)](#) satellite data. Within Europe, the revisit rate ranges from 1 to 3 days ([Copernicus, n.d.](#)) and flood delineations are updated accordingly. Regarding the January 2025 Southern California wildfires, we accessed active wildfire data between December 24, 2024 to February 14, 2025 from the [National Aeronautics and Space Administration \(NASA\) Land, Atmosphere Near real-time Capability for Earth observation \(LANCE\) Fire Information for Resource Management System \(FIRMS\)](#) ([NASA LANCE, 2023](#)). It delivers active fire data on a per-day basis from the [Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer \(MODIS\)](#) on board [NASA’s](#) Aqua and Terra satellites with a spatial resolution of 1km.

3.2 Geoparsing

To identify geographic locations from the collected Bluesky posts, we applied a geoparser on the texts. Geoparsing consists of two main steps: (1) extracting location mentions from text (toponym recognition), and (2) resolving these mentions to geographic coordinates (toponym resolution). Numerous methods have been proposed for this task, often combining deep neural networks for [Named Entity Recognition \(NER\)](#), as implemented in [NLP](#) libraries like spaCy ([Montani, Honnibal, Boyd, Landeghem, & Peters, 2023](#)), with geocoding services such as Nominatim or Google Maps ([Serere, Resch, & Havas, 2023](#)). Our methodology treats extracted geolocations as references to places being discussed in the content. We make no assumptions about the correspondence between the mentioned locations and the user’s physical whereabouts. This distinction is fundamental, as social media users frequently discuss events occurring at remote locations ([Serere & Resch, 2025](#)).

Given the total volume of 676,337 posts, traditional geoparsing methods were not feasible due to cost and performance constraints. For instance, using the Google Maps [API](#) costs between 0.003 and 0.005€ per call ([Google, 2025](#)), which would yield a sum of well over 1,000€ for our geoparsing needs. The [OpenStreetMap \(OSM\) Nominatim API](#) is free but performs slightly worse for geoparsing ([Serere et al., 2023](#)) and is

subject to a rate limit of one request per second (OpenStreetMap Foundation, 2025), making the full process last almost 8 days.

To overcome these limitations, we employed the Irchel Geoparser developed by Gomes (2024), which operates entirely offline and includes a context-aware toponym disambiguation mechanism. The full geoparsing workflow proceeds as follows:

1. Toponyms are extracted using a spaCy [NER](#) pipeline.
2. For each toponym, a local copy of the GeoNames gazetteer database (GeoNames, n.d.) is queried to generate a list of candidate locations using a greedy string matching strategy.
3. Toponym strings are then contextually enriched by capturing surrounding words, while candidate locations are represented using descriptive sentences constructed from gazetteer attributes.
4. These enriched toponym representations are used as input to a fine-tuned Sentence-Transformer embedding model (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), which maps the texts to a semantic embedding space.
5. The candidate location with the highest cosine similarity to the toponym representation is selected as the output.

This method achieves an Accuracy@161km score between 0.51 and 0.87 on several benchmark datasets (Gomes, 2024). The metric indicates the proportion of toponyms resolved within 161 km (100 miles) of the ground truth coordinates. Since spaCy offers [NER](#) models for multiple languages and GeoNames includes multilingual place names, this approach is particularly suitable for processing heterogeneous and multilingual social media content such as that found on Bluesky.

For our analysis, we used the `xx_ent_wiki_sm` multilingual [NER](#) model (F-score 0.83) for the September 2024 Central Europe floods and the `en_core_web_trf` English-language [NER](#) model (F-score 0.90) for the January 2025 Southern California wildfires (Montani et al., 2023). If a post contained multiple location mentions, we represented them as a multipoint geometry.

3.3 Data analysis

The geoparsed posts were analysed through a combination of [NLP](#) and spatio-temporal analysis. Specifically, the analysis pipeline consisted of three main components: (1) disaster-relatedness classification, (2) multilingual emotion detection, and (3) spatial aggregation and filtering.

First, we assessed whether each post was disaster-related using the multilingual `disaster-twitter-xlm-roberta-al` transformer model (Hanny et al., 2024). This model was optimised for short-form textual content and showed strong performance across multiple disaster scenarios and languages, achieving classification accuracies between 0.80 and 0.96 in English, Spanish, German, French, and Italian. Based on the classification results, we constructed daily time series of absolute and relative disaster-related content for each event.

To analyse emotional dynamics over time, we applied the `XLM-EMO` model (Bianchi, Nozza, & Hovy, 2022), a multilingual, multi-label classification model designed for emotion detection in short social media texts. The model identifies four

core emotions (joy, anger, fear, and sadness) and achieves macro F1 scores between 0.8 and 0.9 across 19 languages. Notably, it also demonstrated a degree of generalisability to unseen languages, which is particularly important in our case due to the presence of less-resourced languages such as Czech, Slovak, or Hungarian. We computed the absolute daily number and relative proportion of detected emotions across all posts.

For the spatio-temporal analysis, we retained only those posts geoparsed to the affected regions to ensure geographic relevance. Specifically, we filtered for posts located within California for the wildfire use case and within Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Romania or Hungary for the floods use case. This filtering step ensured that temporal patterns reflected local or regional discourse.

To explore spatial patterns, we aggregated the geoparsed, disaster-related content using the H3 hexagonal spatial index by [Uber \(2023\)](#) at resolutions 4 and 5, which correspond to average edge lengths of approximately 26 km and 9.85 km, respectively. These aggregations enabled visual inspection of spatial hotspots and facilitated comparison with physical disaster impact footprints.

Additionally, we analysed the post metadata on the full datasets to characterise their structure. This included the presence of external links or media attachments, and posting frequency per user. Language distributions were derived to evaluate linguistic diversity and the effectiveness of our multilingual keyword sets.

4 Results

This section presents the main findings of our analysis. We report summary statistics of the collected datasets, followed by spatio-temporal patterns of disaster-related content and emotional dynamics during the two case studies.

4.1 Statistical properties

Table 1 provides summary statistics for the Bluesky datasets collected during the 2024 Central Europe floods and the 2025 Southern California wildfires. The Central Europe floods dataset contained a total of 105,767 posts, while the Southern California wildfires dataset included 570,570 posts – more than five times as many. Despite the difference in scale, both datasets showed similar proportions of disaster-related content, with 22.0% and 23.5% of posts, respectively. A comparable share of posts contained external [Uniform Resource Locators \(URLs\)](#) (23.8% for Central Europe, 24.3% for Southern California) and images (18.4% and 18.6%). The Central Europe floods dataset featured 44,174 unique user handles, compared to 228,356 in the Southern California wildfires dataset. On average, users posted 2.39 and 2.50 times, respectively, suggesting similar posting behaviour across both contexts.

Fig. 2 presents the relative distribution of the top five languages across posts in the two datasets, based on the post metadata. For the 2024 Central Europe floods, English was the dominant language (54.0%), followed by Spanish (16.2%), Portuguese (10.5%), and German (10.2%). Notably, German was the only language from the multilingual keyword list to appear among the top five. Other keyword languages yielded relatively few posts: Polish (137), Hungarian (30), Romanian (6), Slovak (1), and none for Czech.

Table 1 Summary statistics of the [Southern California \(SoCal\)](#) wildfires and Central Europe floods Bluesky datasets.

Statistic	2024 Central Europe floods	2025 SoCal wildfires
Total posts	105,767	570,570
Disaster-related posts	23,247 (22.0%)	133,907 (23.5%)
Posts with external URLs	25,174 (23.8%)	138,645 (24.3%)
Posts with images	19,426 (18.4%)	105,972 (18.6%)
Unique user handles	44,174	228,356
Posts per user	2.39	2.50

In contrast, the 2025 Southern California wildfires dataset consisted mostly of English-language posts (73.9%), with a notable proportion of posts labelled as unknown (*unk* = 19.1%) and a small share in Portuguese (4.0%). This discrepancy partly reflects the design of our keyword search approach: The flood-related keywords for Central Europe were multilingual to account for the region’s linguistic diversity, while the wildfire-related keyword list for Southern California was designed exclusively in English, given the localised nature of the event.

Relative distribution of languages across posts

Fig. 2 Relative distribution of the top five languages across the two datasets based on Bluesky metadata.

4.2 Disaster response

Subsequent to the descriptive statistical analyses, we investigated the response to the disasters on Bluesky in more detail, employing a semantic and emotion analysis approach.

4.2.1 2024 Central Europe floods

Fig. 3 shows the daily proportion of flood-related posts among all posts retrieved each day for the 2024 Central Europe floods. To focus on the impacted region, only posts geoparsed to locations within Central Europe (Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Romania and Hungary) were included in the results. At the very start of the observation window (September 1-9), disaster-related content already made up 15% to 30% of all posts. This can be attributed to our keyword selection, which also yielded disaster-related content from other regions of the world. In accordance with the news about heavy rains and subsequent flooding (September 9–16), this share rose gradually, peaking at almost 80% on September 15. During the subsequent response and recovery period, the share of disaster-related posts declined again, until arriving at its original values at the end of September.

Fig. 3 Daily proportion of disaster-related posts across all posts with a geoparsed location in Central Europe for the 2024 Central Europe floods dataset.

Fig. 4 depicts the daily distribution of emotions over the same period. Here, the patterns were more nuanced. A slight increase in fear could be observed during the main flooding period (September 12-17), whereas the share of joy notably declined. It is also visible that the presence of fear peaked a few days before the event (September 9), suggesting an emotional discussion about a potential flooding prior to the actual rainfall.

Focusing on the geospatial dimension, Fig. 6 shows the aggregated disaster-related content after geoparsing in level 4 H3 grid cells. The majority of disaster-related Bluesky posts were geocoded in Austria and parts of Germany, southern Poland, and northern Switzerland. This shows a particular focus on German-speaking regions. In other areas, particularly in large parts of Romania, northern Poland, Hungary, and Slovakia, there were almost no disaster-related Bluesky posts. It is also noticeable, especially for Germany, Italy and Romania, that many posts were geoparsed in the centre of the country, indicating that the geocodable location was merely the country

Fig. 4 Daily proportion of emotions per day for all posts with a geoparsed location in Central Europe for the 2024 Central Europe floods dataset.

name. The map also shows the flooded areas, which were primarily located in eastern Hungary, western Belarus, eastern Romania, and eastern Germany. In many of these areas, however, there were hardly any or no relevant Bluesky posts available. Fig. A1 in the appendix shows the same aggregation on H3 level 5, which demonstrates a sparser spatial distribution of Bluesky posts with a noticeable predominance of urban regions.

The number of disaster-related posts was generally considerably higher for regions where flooding occurred. While the median number of posts per H3 grid cell (level 4) was 0 for both flooded and non-flooded areas, clear differences emerged at higher percentiles. At the 99% percentile of post counts (i.e. the top 1% of values), flooded regions had 50.84 posts, compared to only 18.96 posts in non-affected areas. This contrast also persisted on the more fine-grained H3 level 5. As shown in Fig. 5, most regions had only very few posts, but flooded areas were more likely to exhibit a higher number of posts.

Fig. 7 distinguishes the spatial distribution of disaster-related posts on a weekly basis on H3 grid (level 4). A substantial increase in disaster-related posts in the second week of September, which corresponded to the most severe flooding, was particularly noticeable for Austria, the Czech Republic, and southern Germany.

Fig. 5 Relation between post count and presence of flooding on H3 grid (level 4). Regions without posts were excluded for legibility.

Fig. 6 Count of disaster-related Bluesky posts on H3 grid (level 4).

Fig. 7 Count of disaster-related posts on a weekly basis with a geoparsed location in Central Europe for the 2024 Central Europe floods dataset on H3 grid (level 4).

4.2.2 2025 Southern California wildfires

Fig. 8 shows a time series of the daily relative proportion of disaster-related posts in total Bluesky activity. Again, to ensure geographic relevance, the data was filtered to include only posts geoparsed to locations within California. For reference, the number of active wildfires identified by the NASA FIRMS (NASA LANCE, 2023) is also depicted. The comparison reveals a strong alignment between wildfire activity and social media discourse. The proportion of disaster-related posts increased markedly in early January 2025, coinciding with a peak in the number of active fires. At its highest point, disaster-related content accounted for nearly 60% of all crawled posts. This peak was followed by a gradual decline in both wildfire activity and the relative share of disaster-related posts through mid-February.

Fig. 8 Relative proportion of disaster-related posts across all posts with a geoparsed location in California for the 2025 Southern California wildfire dataset. For reference, the number of active fires in California as identified by the NASA FIRMS is shown.

A time series of the emotions present in *all* local posts, including both disaster-related and unrelated content, is depicted in Fig. 9. A clear shift in user response over the course of the disaster is visible. The relative prevalence of fear and anger rose significantly during the wildfire period, comprising up to 30% to 40% of posts. Sadness maintained a moderate presence throughout the observation window but declined slightly after the peak event. Joy was very present in the beginning (almost 80%), but dropped down to less than 30% when the wildfires peaked. Throughout January, however, the presence of joy rose back to about 70%. Posts with no emotions consistently stayed at a fraction of 10% to 15%.

Fig. 11 shows the total amount of disaster-related posts aggregated in level 5 H3 grid cells. Due to the higher number of Bluesky posts, a more fine-grained H3 level was used than in Fig. 6. The more aggregated map based on H3 level 4 can be found in the appendix (see Fig. A2). The highest number of relevant posts was clearly attributable to the largest population centres in California, i.e. Los Angeles, San Diego, and San Francisco. This corresponds, at least in part, with the most affected regions, as the

Fig. 9 Relative proportion of emotions per day across all posts with a geoparsed location in California for the 2025 Southern California wildfire dataset.

north-west of Los Angeles was particularly impacted by wildfires. However, other areas with high fire activity, particularly between Redding and Sacramento, tended to coincide with low Bluesky activity. However, it can be stated that there was an almost continuous, albeit quantitatively fluctuating, coverage of disaster-related posts, which constitutes a major difference from the Central European use cases and their regional data sparsity.

Once again, the number of disaster-related posts was generally higher for regions where wildfires occurred. Fig. 10 indicates a relation between post count and wildfires, with the relative amount of H3 grid cells in affected regions rising in correspondence with higher post counts. On H3 level 4, the median post count was 4.5 for affected and 0 for non-affected areas. For the 90% percentile, the difference was 198.1 to 6.0. This also held true for H3 level 5, where the 90% percentile was at 38.4 for the affected regions and 1.0 for areas without wildfires. On the other hand, the maximal number of disaster-related posts was much higher in non-affected regions (47,226 to 3,789).

Fig. 12 shows that the spatial distribution of disaster-related Bluesky posts remained relatively stable over time. However, in the second week of January, the region surrounding Los Angeles emerged as a clear hotspot of posting activity, aligning with the spread of wildfires. The number of relevant posts clearly decreased towards the end of the month, when the situation came under control.

Fig. 10 Relation between post count and presence of wildfire on H3 grid (level 4). Regions without posts were excluded for legibility.

Fig. 11 Count of disaster-related Bluesky posts on H3 grid (level 5). Wildfire footprints derived from MODIS are shown transparently to indicate areas with higher amount of relevant pixels.

Fig. 12 Count of disaster-related posts on a weekly basis with a geoparsed location in California.

5 Discussion

Our discussion is divided into a discussion of the results of our analyses and a discussion of the methodology.

5.1 Discussion of the results

Across the two selected natural disaster events, the 2025 Southern California wildfires and the 2024 Central Europe floods, we generally observed high volumes of disaster-related content with strong temporal and emotional alignment to the disasters. When filtered by extracted locations within each area of interest, the proportion of disaster-related posts in the retrieved corpus was low (about 1% to 25%) before the occurrence of any local disaster and rose significantly (between 60% to 80%) during the main impact period. For the California wildfires use case, the proportion of disaster-related content presented a notable spike that peaked even quicker than the actual wildfire presence. This indicates capabilities of Bluesky for early warning and event detection in wildfire scenarios, though this effect might be limited to densely populated areas like California and the [USA](#). Further research is required to assess the volume of posts for more remote disaster scenarios. For the 2024 Central Europe floods, the rise in locally geoparsed and disaster-related posts was more gradual and only peaked after the onset of heavy rainfall. This suggests that most of the posts were published in response to the disaster as it unfolded, rather than in anticipation of it. A smaller portion of posts also talked about weather warnings prior to the actual rainfall. Similar patterns could be observed with regard to emotions. For both use cases, the proportion of fearful posts increased significantly after the disaster onset. In contrast, the proportion of joyful posts notably decreased. The occurrence of floods or wildfires, therefore, resulted in a notable shift in public sentiment on the Bluesky platform. Similarly, there was a slight increase in the proportion of angry posts slightly after the main disaster period, partly due to a minor rise of disaster-related political content.

The examination of the spatial dimension revealed certain differences between the use cases. While there was relatively continuous spatial coverage of disaster-related Bluesky posts in California, the geometries in Europe were much more clustered. Many regions, particularly in Eastern Europe, had very little to no disaster-related activity on Bluesky. This indicates that the platform does not (yet) have enough user penetration in some countries to be able to derive significant conclusions for disaster management. In other areas, especially densely populated areas in German-speaking countries, the data situation appears to be more promising. Due to the large US user base, this seems to hold even more true for North America. Nevertheless, it was noticeable that urban regions stood out in the spatial representation. Although this mirrors a tendency in many Twitter analyses ([Malik, Lamba, Nakos, & Pfeffer, 2021](#)), it is likely attributable to the need for geoparsing and the more frequent occurrence of urban toponyms in Bluesky posts.

Our overall findings are in line with previous studies conducted with Twitter data. For instance, [Resch et al. \(2018\)](#) validated their Twitter analysis on the Napa Valley earthquake with footprints by the [United States Geological Survey \(USGS\)](#), finding considerable concurrence through spatial hot spot analysis. Similarly, [Havas and Resch](#)

(2021) showed that the number of Tweets rose right at the occurrence of an earthquake in Italy. They also demonstrated a clear spatial overlap between disaster-related Tweets, identified through topic modelling, and areas affected by Hurricane Harvey’s landfall. In their study in Seoul, [Kwon and Kang \(2016-04\)](#) found that Twitter data could even predict an urban flood event two hours in advance. [Schmidt et al. \(2025\)](#) stated that Twitter data can be used to identify wildfires early, at least for regions with significant Twitter activity. The rising amount of disaster-related posts in Fig. 3, as well as the existing disaster-related activity in the first week of January for the California use case (see Fig 12), before the actual onset of the event may be an indication that Bluesky data could be used for similar prediction purposes.

High-level statistical and semantic analysis of the retrieved datasets showed a similar fraction of external links and images, as well as a comparable number of unique users. We therefore assume a degree of consistency in user behaviour across different disaster scenarios on Bluesky. However, substantial differences were observed in terms of dataset size and language distribution. Notably, the vast majority of posts for both use cases were authored in English. This is consistent with user demographic data indicating that Bluesky’s user base is heavily skewed towards the [USA](#) (73.99% of active users) ([Semrush, 2025](#)). The relatively high number of posts in Portuguese and Spanish also mirrors common language distributions in Twitter data ([Hong, Convertino, & Chi, 2021](#)). While these numbers largely reflect underlying platform demographics, they may have been reinforced by the predominance of English-language keywords, particularly in the Southern California wildfires use case. Regardless, it seems that disaster events in regions with low Bluesky user penetration are likely to be underrepresented in the retrieved data. This limitation is reflected by the low number of posts retrieved using non-English search terms, despite targeted efforts to include multiple Central and Eastern European languages. Specifically, we only retrieved 137 posts in Polish, 30 in Hungarian, 6 in Romanian, 1 in Slovak, and none in Czech. These numbers illustrate a limited adoption or visibility of Bluesky in Central and Eastern European regions, which has direct implications for the platform’s utility in monitoring disasters in these areas. Future work should identify which regions are especially underrepresented and explore the possible reasons as well as ways to improve data coverage.

5.2 Discussion of the methodology

Our methodology is subject to both platform-specific limitations and methodological constraints. Most importantly, as of June 2025, the Bluesky search [API](#) lacks a functional pagination mechanism, which makes it impossible to guarantee the completeness of the retrieved posts matching a given query. This also affects the reproducibility of the data collection process, as it is not transparent how exactly the posts in the result set are ranked. In addition, post-retrieval is currently restricted to keyword-based queries, which presents challenges for multilingual data acquisition. Although the [API](#) is invariant to diacritics and variations of letters, it still searches for exact word matches, limiting its ability to capture inflexions. Consequently, keywords must be curated manually, which remains a major practical constraint. The relatively high amount of Spanish and Portuguese posts for the 2024 Central Europe floods also

unveiled the issue that the same keywords may occur in different languages but with distinct meanings. For instance, *eső* in Hungarian means *rain* and *eso* in Spanish means *that*. Similarly, *mentés* means *rescue* in Hungarian, but *mentes* in Portuguese means *minds* or *you lie*. Since the Bluesky search API is invariant to diacritics, plenty of posts that were unrelated to the actual keyword were retrieved. This limitation could be circumvented by filtering for posts only in specific languages. However, the post language metadata from Bluesky proved partly inaccurate during our data retrieval, e.g. some posts in English were labelled as Portuguese. This is because Bluesky does not have a standardised language tagging system so far, and up to three language labels can only be selected manually by users at the time of posting. Additionally, the platform allows for the usage of custom clients, which may handle language tagging differently or omit it entirely (Failla & Rossetti, 2024). Relying on pre-existing language labels for filtering, therefore, bears the danger of missing important content. We therefore primarily utilised downstream semantic analysis instead.

The restriction to keyword-based search also limits the scope of potential analyses. It is currently not feasible to retrieve an exhaustive set of *all* Bluesky posts within a given time frame, which prevents the estimation of overall platform activity and the establishment of meaningful baselines. This also affected efforts to apply topic modelling on the retrieved data. Due to the constrained semantic space introduced by keyword filtering, there was a considerable overlap between all topics, and the model failed to produce coherent or well-separated themes. This problem was also discussed by Li et al. (2018), who argued that a lack of diversity in words, combined with the linguistic noise present in social media data (e.g. words like "haha"), can lead to inaccurate topic estimates. Similar issues were observed in location extraction. Since the keyword list for the 2025 Southern California wildfires use case also included place names like "Los Angeles", the distribution of geoparsed coordinates was heavily skewed toward these locations. This could potentially obscure mentions of less prominent but also affected areas.

Geospatial analysis was furthermore limited by the lack of reliable location references in the post metadata. Although we were able to extract spatial information from the texts through geoparsing, this remains a methodological pitfall. We recognise that users often post about disasters occurring elsewhere, as shown by Serere and Resch (2025), which complicates the interpretation of spatial patterns in geoparsed content. Our methodology, therefore, treats the mentioned locations merely as references to places, not as indicators of where a post was made. Consequently, extracted geolocations cannot be equated with user locations, as was often assumed in previous research on Twitter data (Schmidt, Zorenböhmer, Arifi, & Resch, 2023; Serere et al., 2023). They also cannot be considered representative of the general user population distribution (Karami et al., 2021). Additionally, location mentions in text are usually less granular than geotagging locations (X. Hu et al., 2023; Y. Hu & Wang, 2020) and might suffer from a degree of ambiguity. Even if a place is mentioned, it is not necessarily relevant in a disaster context. Future work should therefore investigate geoparsing methods that take this context into account. Moreover, the relationship between posting activity and natural disaster occurrence is hard to quantify. Most studies utilise a mixture of qualitative and quantitative methodology for this reason

(Acikara, Xia, Yigitcanlar, & Hon, 2023). As our research explores the general suitability of Bluesky data for geographically informed disaster management, we followed a similar methodology.

Future studies should explore the use and development of more granular tools for semantic and emotion analysis in disaster response. For instance, instead of evaluating the disaster-relatedness of posts, a multilingual model for multi-class relevance classification could be developed (similar to Blomeier, Schmidt, & Resch, 2024). This would allow for more granular insights into disaster-related communication on social media and also provide more actionable information to emergency responders. Similarly, aspect-based emotion analysis might be employed over document-level emotion analysis to better understand emotional discourse (Zorenböhmer, Schmidt, & Resch, 2025). Currently, these methods face severe limitations with regard to multilingualism. Our analysis approach could also be adapted for real-time monitoring of social media via Bluesky’s firehose streaming API and consequently event detection. The post metadata available through the firehose API is currently more limited than for the search API, though. Lastly, our research remains content-focused. Follow-up studies could investigate information diffusion and network effects for disaster-related content on Bluesky. In addition, a thematic extension of this study would be of great relevance, as georeferenced Twitter data has been used in numerous fields of research, for example, in epidemiology or political science. Verifying the suitability of Bluesky data for such research fields would enable a certain continuity of research or even generate new questions. For this purpose, however, a closer look at the socio-demographic aspects of Bluesky users is also relevant in order to take potential biases into account.

6 Conclusion

This study assessed the potential of Bluesky as a novel data source for disaster-related social media analysis by applying a multilingual, multimodal analysis pipeline to two recent natural disasters: the September 2024 Central Europe floods and the January 2025 Southern California wildfires.

Regarding **RQ1**, our findings confirm that Bluesky holds considerable potential as a data source for (geo-)social media analysis in disaster management. Despite its relatively recent public launch, the platform already generates substantial volumes of disaster-related content, clear temporal patterns aligned with real-world events and emotionally rich discourse. The semantic and statistical properties of the retrieved datasets closely mirrored those found in earlier studies using Twitter data, suggesting some continuity in user behaviour across platforms.

For **RQ2**, we found that location mentions in Bluesky posts can support geospatial analysis of disaster-related content through geoparsing, particularly in regions with high platform usage. Geoparsed locations generally aligned with disaster impact areas in regions with high user coverage. However, spatial analysis was limited by geographical differences in the platform’s use and the keyword-based retrieval method, which introduced selection biases and skewed place name distributions. Thus, while location mentions are useful, their effectiveness is constrained by these platform limitations and methodological factors.

With regard to **RQ3**, our analysis revealed distinct semantic, emotional, spatial, and temporal patterns for both disasters. Disaster-related discourse followed the temporal progression of the events and showed strong emotional fluctuations, particularly in expressions of fear, anger and joy. While the semantic, emotional, and temporal patterns were relatively similar, there were strong differences in the spatial dimension between the two use cases. The California use case showed a certain spatial continuity in the availability of disaster-related posts. This also corresponded well with the actual wildfire centres and the temporal progression of the event. For the flood use case in Central Europe, the spatial distribution was much more clustered, especially in urban areas and German-speaking countries. For many regions in Eastern Europe, there were hardly any posts that could be georeferenced, despite the consideration of the respective languages in the crawling process.

To mitigate geographic and demographic biases, future work should aim to expand geo-social media analysis to multiple social media platforms, combining Bluesky with other sources like TikTok, Reddit or Telegram. The development of additional crawling strategies could also address the current limitations of the platform. Moreover, real-time monitoring of the Bluesky firehose may enable continuous early warning and improved rapid situational awareness for emergency responders. In a much broader context, our study highlights the promise of Bluesky as a new decentralised social media platform with open [API](#) access for researchers and the general public. These characteristics position it as a compelling foundation for future social media research.

Declarations

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Data availability. The raw Bluesky datasets supporting the conclusions of this article are available on Zenodo under the [Digital Object Identifier \(DOI\) 10.5281/zenodo.17227256](#).

Material availability. The materials of this study will be made available by the authors on request.

Code availability. The Python code for the methodology of this work is available on [GitHub](#).

Author contribution. Conceptualisation, D.H. and S.S.; methodology, D.H. and S.S.; software, D.H. and S.S.; validation, D.H. and S.S.; formal analysis, D.H. and S.S.; investigation, D.H. and S.S.; resources, B.R. and S.S.; data curation, D.H. and S.S.; writing—original draft preparation, D.H. and S.S.; writing—review and editing, D.H., S.S. and B.R.; visualisation, D.H. and S.S.; supervision, B.R.; project administration, B.R.; funding acquisition, B.R. and S.S.

Appendix A Supplementary figures

Fig. A1 Count of disaster-related Bluesky posts in Central Europe throughout September 2024 on H3 grid (level 5).

Fig. A2 Count of disaster-related Bluesky posts on H3 grid (level 4). Wildfire footprints derived from MODIS are shown transparently to indicate areas with a higher amount of relevant pixels.

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